

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

A BRIEF OVERVIEW OF THE WORKS OF AZERBAIJAN TOPONOMS

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Abstract

In the study of the main regularities of geographical names operating in the toponymic system of Azerbaijan, in most cases touching on diachronicity, primarily local pronunciation forms, functional-structural types and "folk etymologies" that play an important role in folk etymology are considered. In compiling the names used from the included field materials, the development and systematization of the subject is handled from a simultaneous perspective.

Most of the materials of this nature, reflecting the toponymic landscape of Azerbaijan, were obtained during trips organized by the Nasimi Institute of Linguistics of the National Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Azerbaijan in 1967-1979.

Later, the special requests prepared were sent to different regions of the republic and the way of receiving their answers was concentrated in a number of regions during the period of individual missions.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, toponym, "Kitabi-Dada Gorgud", saga, phonetic composition.

In the study of the problem, the toponymic card file compiled under the leadership of R. Yuzbashov and B. Budagov at the National Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Azerbaijan and covering several zones of the republic had a certain role.

11th-12th The epic "Kitabi-Dada Gorgud", which dates back to the 16th century and in which many place names of Azerbaijan are written, has great scientific importance in terms of reflecting the phonetic composition more accurately and transparently. In other words, it is possible to determine where objects belong with the help of ouconyms, oronyms and hydronyms mentioned in connection with events.

In this epic, the phonetic structure of most of the names, the meanings and structures of the words, and the grammatical structures used in the creation of the lexical units from which these place names are derived are used without any changes in our modern place name system and language.

For example, Agca Castle, Ag Gaya, Alinca Castle, Aladag, Bayat, Barda, Garadag, Kara Dera, Demir Gava, Darvand, Deresham, Ganja, Kara Deniz, Chesme, Mardin Castle, Oguz Elleri, Surmeli, etc. [3, 181-183]

As it is known, from the beginning of the XIII century, Azerbaijan was attacked by the Mongols and was soon occupied by them. The famous Mongol historian of the 13th century Rashideddin, who personally participated in these marches, mentioned the names of a number of Mongolian and Turkic tribes that participated in that movement while describing the events.

It is clear from the research conducted in this field that most of the tribe names mentioned by the author (Tangit, Uriyat, Sunit, Karig, Kurgan, Karkin, Kingit, Chobani, Juryat, Jalair, Tatar, Ongut, Dolan, etc.) [3, 452] of Azerbaijan was the basis for the creation of many ethnotoponyms. For example: Oriyat, Kungut, Zunud, Guzey, Garkhun, Sumgait, Malik Choban, Corat, Jaleir, Gurgan, Dolanar, Ungutlu, etc. It should be noted that the toponyms of Karabakh, Arasbar, Astara,

Khilla and others were recorded for the first time by Rashidaddin.

Zakariyya al-Qazvini, who lived in the same century, wrote that near Ganja there is a place called Kharrek, and the Daruran River (now Ganjachay) flows from there. [1,54].

In the 16th century historian Sharafkhan ibn Shamseddin Bidli's work "Sharafname", in addition to the above, toponyms like Agdash, Arpachay, Kyzylagac and others were mentioned. [1,54].

One of the works belonging to this period is Fazlullah ibn Ruzbihan Khunji's "Tarihi-Alam-Arayi Ani" work. The work is rich in facts related to Azerbaijani toponymy and ethnonymy: Alinja, Arvana Mountain, Balash Desert, Bargushad, Gozal Dere, Gulustan Castle, Gurgan, Zanjan River, Gajar tribe, Aggoyunlu, Karagoyunlu, Turkmen, Mosullu, Sulut, Shuragöl, Khani, etc. [2, 162-165]

The book "Tarikh-e Sheikh Uwais" by the Azerbaijani historian Abu Bakr al-Qutbi al-Ahari of the 16th century and the book "The Campaign of Amir Yashbey" by Muhammad al-Khalabi of the 15th century can be used as a reliable source for studying our toponyms and ethnonyms.

The book "Kitab talkhis al-asr wa asaib al-malik al-gahhar" by the medieval geographer, Azerbaijani scientist (XIV-XV centuries) Abdurrashid al-Bakuvi has a special place among the works rich in valuable facts for the toponymy and ethnonymy of Azerbaijan and its historical geography. The author has corrected many mistakes made by Ghazvini in the registration of place-names, provided new rich information about the cities of Azerbaijan and other places of the country, the roads passing near the Caspian Sea, and especially the city of Baku.

Let's consider some of those names: Bakuya, Khazar, Darband, Shirvan, Mugan, Shaburan, Khazar country, Tatar country, Nakjuvan, Kharkan, Darman, Shiz, Bazz, Baylakan, Janza, etc. [4, 37] The famous

Ottoman historian Ibrahim Efendi Pechavi's work "History" (XVI-XVII centuries) is one of the characteristic sources in this regard. As noted by Academician Ziya Bunyadov, it is very difficult to assess the importance of Ibrahim Efendi Pechavi's "History" for studying the history of Azerbaijan, neighboring countries and regions.

Due to its importance, it does not only provide rare material about the conquest marches of the Ottomans to Azerbaijan and the Ottoman-Persian wars conducted in its territory. At the same time, in Pechavi's work, the names of Azerbaijani cities, the life of the city population, ancient and new fortresses, local judges, trade, professional crafts, etc. There is also rich information about [3, 47-48]

The mentioned work also provides information about the oikonomic objects: Kizylagac pasture, Kazan castle, Uchan place, Goytepe parking lot, Dokuz Ulum river, Van castle, Kicichchinar, Garabaghlar circle, Jildirduzu, Zayam city, Gabirri river, Sheki castle, Kanig river, Demirgapi castle, Mahmudabad plain, Tabriz fortress, etc.

In terms of recording our geographical and ethnic names, the archaeological documents of the 16th-19th centuries are especially valuable. In those documents, the names of a large number of Azerbaijani toponyms and microtoponyms are mentioned, and certain information is given about the tribes and similar groups living in different zones of this territory. At the same time, it is possible to add information about geographical and ethnic names of our region in the travel notes of medieval travelers.

After the annexation of Azerbaijan to Russia, in the works written by Russian officials about the life and everyday life of state peasants, in statistical descriptions of individual accidents, in general works written about Transcaucasia, facts and other official documents, etc. A large amount of information was given about Azerbaijani onomastic units, especially toponyms and ethnonyms closely related to toponym creation, and the toponymic and ethnonymic landscape of the period was widely reflected in those sources.

From the second half of the 19th century until the establishment of Soviet power in Azerbaijan, the published collections contain rich facts about the names of places, tribes, generations, ethnic groups and peoples of Azerbaijan.

Among them, the published works of A. Shifner, P. Uslar, E. Weydenbaum, Dorn, A. Dirr, N. Zeylits and other prominent Caucasian scholars, etymological analysis of geographical names and terms are given in the

relevant sections of most geographical names. anthologies are considered valuable sources for teaching toponyms and ethnonyms of the Caucasus, including Azerbaijan.

The toponymic picture of the Caucasus, including Azerbaijan at the end of the 19th century and the first decade of the 20th century, is more widely reflected in the monumental work "Alphabetical order of the map of the Caucasus region" published by the Caucasus Military Topography Department published by D. Pagyrev in 1913 in Tbilisi.

Here, 34,000 toponyms recorded in various works were systematized, their exact location was determined based on the map provided at the end, and thus a valuable resource was created. Based on this work, it is possible to obtain interesting scientific results and carry out serious research about the toponymic systems of the Caucasus, as well as its separate regions, the phonetic structure of names, the lexical composition and main semantic groups of the words used in toponym creation, the relationships between toposystems, and other issues.

A valuable aspect of the work is that, based on its materials, it is possible to determine with great accuracy the distribution areas of a number of peoples of the Caucasus, especially the Turkic-speaking ethnic groups, which specific areas of the zone they live in, which macro, micro and elemental areas, and the names of many Turkic ethnic groups.

On the other hand, the main mass of geographical names reflected in the dictionary is made up of Turkic-language toponyms and scattered everywhere, at the same time, it once again confirms that Turkic-speaking peoples dominate this area and that they are among the oldest inhabitants of the area.

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